

NNLM Disaster Resources

NNLM Emergency Preparedness Guide

This is an online collection of resources and tools that are relevant to disaster and emergency management.

MedlinePlus Resources

MedlinePlus provides preparedness information in plain language for patients and their families and friends about diseases, conditions, and wellness.

Topics include:

- Earthquakes, Floods, Hurricanes, Tornadoes, Wildfires, and Winter Weather.

NNLM Virtual Disaster Preparedness Forum 2025

See this past year's Virtual Disaster Preparedness Forum recordings at the link above or use the YouTube link to view past recordings.

 YouTube

For more information or resources on disaster preparedness, please visit [NNLM.gov](https://www.nlm.nih.gov) or speak with a representative from your RML.